

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF PHONOLOGICAL AWARENESS ON LANGUAGE ACQUISITION IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

This research investigates the impact of phonological awareness on language acquisition in children. It examines the development of phonological awareness skills in relation to language proficiency and explores potential applications for improving language education. The study combines quantitative assessments of phonological awareness with qualitative analysis of language acquisition in a sample of 200 elementary school children.

Keywords: Phonological Awareness, Language Acquisition, Children, Language Proficiency, Education.

Introduction

Phonological awareness, the ability to recognize and manipulate the sounds in spoken language, plays a crucial role in language development. This study delves into the relationship between phonological awareness and language acquisition in children. The research is motivated by the significance of these skills for educational success and effective language instruction.

This section reviews existing research on phonological awareness and its connection to language acquisition. It covers studies that have investigated the development of phonological awareness in children and its effects on vocabulary and reading skills.

The research methodology used in this study is described, including participant selection, data collection procedures, and the phonological awareness assessments. The combination of quantitative and qualitative methods is detailed, explaining the rationale for this approach.

This section presents the quantitative findings of the study, focusing on the development of phonological awareness in children and its correlation with language proficiency. Qualitative data from interviews and language assessments are discussed in relation to these results.

The results are analyzed in the context of the existing literature, emphasizing the role of phonological awareness in language acquisition. Implications for language education and early intervention programs are explored. The limitations of the study and avenues for further research are also considered.

The study concludes by summarizing the key findings, emphasizing the critical role of phonological awareness in language acquisition, and suggesting strategies for enhancing language instruction. It highlights the potential for educational interventions to improve children's language development.

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